

Information-Theoretic Selection of High-Dimensional Spectral Features for Structural Recognition

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Abstract

Pattern recognition methods often deal with samples consisting of thousands of features. Therefore, the reduction of their dimensionality becomes crucial to make the data sets tractable. Feature selection techniques remove the irrelevant and noisy features and select a subset of features which describe better the samples and produce a better classification performance. In this paper, we propose a novel feature selection method for supervised classification within an information-theoretical framework. Mutual information is exploited for measuring the statistical relation between a subset of features and the class labels of the samples. Traditionally it has been measured for ranking single features; however, in most data sets the features are not independent and their combination provides much more information about the class than the sum of their individual prediction power. We analyze the use of different estimation methods which bypass the density estimation and estimate entropy and mutual information directly from the set of samples. These methods allow us to efficiently evaluate multivariate sets of thousands

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of features.

Within this framework we experiment with spectral graph features extracted from 3D shapes. Most of the existing graph classification techniques rely on the graph attributes. We use unattributed graphs to show what is the contribution of each spectral feature to graph classification. Apart from succeeding to classify graphs from shapes relying only on their structure, we test to what extent the set of selected spectral features are robust to perturbations of the dataset.

Keywords:

feature selection, pattern classification, Information Theory, mutual information,, entropy, structure, spectral features

1. Introduction

This paper proposes a novel method for supervised structural classification, which has become a main concern in different areas. Graph representations are used in different fields like ecology, proteomics, communications, natural language processing and many others. There are two sources of information in a graph: its structure, which represent the internal organization of the pattern under study, and its attributes on concrete nodes and edges. In the present work we study a set of spectral graph features which describe purely structural aspects of a graph, and analyze them within a novel information-theoretic feature selection method that we propose.

We experiment on graphs extracted from 3D models. The reason is that the increasing amount of 3D models – nowadays widely used in video games, virtual worlds, cultural heritage, as well as medicine and bioinformatics –

arise the need for 3D object classification techniques. Though some 3D databases include labels describing each object, in general manual classification is unfeasible due to the amount of human effort required. Thus, *content-based* automatic 3D shape classification is a problem with increasing interest.

In this context, we propose a scheme for supervised 3D shape classification in multi-class problems, based on (i) content-based shape description via spectral features extracted from Reeb graphs, and (ii) information-theoretic feature selection. The scheme is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: From left to right, 3D description via graph extraction, computation of histograms of spectral features, feature selection.

Concerning shape description (i), three types of Reeb graphs (denoted *Sphere*, *Baricenter* and *Geodesic* in Figure 1, left) are extracted from each 3D object. Only structural graph information is taken into account: this leads to a completely non-rigid comparison among objects. For each graph, nine different measures are calculated and transformed into histograms. In this way we are able to characterize 3D objects according to different aspects, and without dependence on the number and order of the graph nodes.

Then, we let the feature selection process (ii) decide which binning from

which measure and from which graph to discard (Figure 1, right). We do so by exploiting information theory to filter those features which do not contribute to the separability of the objects into classes. In particular, we introduce a *filter feature selection* method which estimates the mutual information between the feature set and the class labels using a bypass entropy estimation method.

We test our approach to multi-class classification on the SHREC dataset [1] with up to 15 different classes of 3D objects.

1.1. Contribution

The contribution of this work is twofold, that is, it concerns both 3D shape classification and information theory-based feature selection.

Concerning 3D shape classification, we demonstrate the feasibility of multi-class 3D classification based on unattributed graphs and purely structural spectral features. No metric information is used. Our main contribution in this context is to show to what extent purely topological information suffices for achieving a significant classification performance or to improving the performance of a yet existing method. To that end, given a bag of spectral features each one characterizing globally the graph we address the following questions: (1) what is the importance of each feature for classification purposes?, and (2) is that importance dependent of how we extract the Reeb graph?

Although feature analysis plays a fundamental role in pattern classification, there are few studies about this topic in structured patterns, mainly when graphs are not attributed, an exception being [2] where different spectral features are investigated for embedding purposes. This is why this paper

presents a novel feature selection method based on information theory and mutual information estimate. Whereas traditionally mutual information has been evaluated between a single feature and the class label [3, 4, 5], here we estimate the mutual information for the entire set of features to select. This is an important advantage in feature selection [6], as we also take into account the interaction between features. We propose a bypass entropy estimator independent of parameter settings and distributional assumptions, and combine it with a backward feature selection strategy, which result in a powerful method for feature selection.

As a final contribution, in the Appendix we present an experimental comparison between different entropy estimators, namely the Kozachenko-Leonenko k -NN entropy estimator and the Stowell-Plumbley k -d partitioning entropy estimator.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. After a short discussion on some related works (Section 2), in Section 3 we detail the first step of our classification technique, that is, 3D description: we detail Reeb graph extraction and graph characterization via spectral features. Section 4 deals with the second step of the technique, that is, we discuss our feature selection procedure. Additional details about the feature selection criterion and a comparison of entropy estimators are presented in Appendix A. The experiments, analysis of the results and discussion are presented in Section 5. Finally, we summarize the conclusions in Section 6.

2. Related work

There are different approaches to 3D object description [7]. Some consist of extracting global and local features from the shape and using their distributions to characterize the objects [8]. Other popular techniques use image-based descriptors [9, 10]. Recently, techniques based on diffusion geometry gained consensus for the description of deformable objects [11]. Nevertheless, as shapes are mentally coded in terms of relevant parts and their spatial configuration, or structure, there is a growing consensus toward structural descriptors based on graphs in the computer vision, computer graphics and pattern recognition literature [12, 13, 14, 15]. Examples include *model graphs* [16], *skeletal graphs* [17] and *curve skeletons* [18, 19]. We point the reader to [20] for a survey on graph extraction.

In this paper, we use Reeb graphs [21, 22, 13], which describe the topology of an object according to the critical points of a real function defined on the object itself. We use different real functions, in order to capture different aspects of the 3D objects under study. Though the nodes and edges of Reeb graphs can be associated with attributes referring to geometric properties [23, 21], here we deal with purely structural information, that is, we use unattributed graphs and extract from them features that rely only on structure. The kind of features which we exploit come from spectral graph theory, which aims at the characterization of the properties of unweighted graphs by means of the eigenspace of the adjacency matrix or the Laplacian matrix [24]. By not keeping any attribute information we can make a detailed analysis of the contribution of each spectral feature to graph classification and we can test to what extent pure structure is useful for discrimination

between graphs.

2.1. Feature selection

Supervised feature selection aims to improve the classification performance of a set of patterns given their class labels. The primary problem of feature selection is defining the criterion which evaluates a feature set. It must decide whether a feature subset is suitable for the classification problem, or not. The optimal criterion for such purpose would be the Bayesian error rate which is the ultimate criterion for discrimination, however, it is not useful as a cost, due to the non-linearity of the $\max(\cdot)$ function. Thus, some alternative cost function has to be used. The ultimate criterion for feature selection is the mutual information between the features and the class label [6]. Mutual information can be expressed as

$$I(\vec{S}; C) = H(C) - H(C|\vec{S})$$

and $H(\vec{C})$ is the entropy of the class labels which do not depend on the feature subspace \vec{S} . Note that mutual information maximization is equivalent to the minimization of the upper bound of the Bayesian error obtained by Hellman and Raviv (1970) [25]: $E(\vec{S}) \leq H(C|\vec{S})/2$, with \vec{S} the vector of selected features and C is the class of the sample. There is a Bayesian error lower bound as well, obtained by Fano (1961) [26], and it is also related to mutual information.

Most approaches based on mutual information assume some kind of independence between the features. However this is not true in most cases and this kind of assumptions usually imply the selection of feature sets with very limited discrimination power. There are several approximations which relax

the independence assumption by estimating, for example, the redundancy between the selected features but they still evaluate mutual information between pairs of features [3, 4, 5]. Without assuming any kind of independence, in this paper we succeed to estimate mutual information even for high dimensional data sets, by using information theory [27, 28] as a theoretical framework.

The most similar feature selection approach to ours is [29] where they do not need to assume independency among features under certain constraints of application. Their criterion is equivalent to mutual information when the search order is forwards by starting from the empty set and adding one feature in each iteration. With our proposal we go beyond this constraint and we show the benefits. A recent list of other information-theoretic feature selection methods can be found in [30]. In their work they also propose a feature selection method which involves mutual information estimation, however their estimation relies on probability distributions from fixed-width histograms. Our approach to entropy estimation differs substantially and we explain its advantages and study entropy estimation in depth.

In a previous work [31], some of the authors already proposed to use a mutual information criterion based on bypass entropy estimation. However, in [31] the criterion was only applied to forward feature selection, for which the mutual information criterion must be coincident with the mRMR (min-Redundancy Max Relevance) criterion [29]. Note that mRMR cannot be applied backwards, and this is a serious limitation since forward selection is very sensitive to local maxima and initialization (the first selected feature determines the remainder). On the contrary, in this paper we show the

potential of the mutual information criterion for a backward search order. Moreover, in [31] the entropy estimation was based on MST (Minimal Spanning Tree), whereas in the current paper we use a different bypass entropy estimator, independent of parameter settings and distributional assumptions. The combination of a different search order and a different bypass entropy estimator result in a more powerful method for feature selection.

3. 3D shape description

In what follows, we explain how we extract Reeb graphs from 3D objects and next we detail the spectral features that we use to characterize those graphs.

3.1. Reeb graphs

Given a surface \mathcal{S} and a real function $f : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the *Reeb graph* (RG) [32] represents the topology of \mathcal{S} through a graph structure whose nodes correspond to the critical points of f . When f is differentiable, the critical points are located in correspondence of topological changes of S , such as birth, join, split and death of connected components of the surface. Hence, RGs describe the *global* topological structure of \mathcal{S} , while also coding *local* features identified by f . RGs are becoming popular in several application domains including shape comparison, segmentation and visualisation. A detailed overview of mathematical properties, computational techniques and applications of Reeb graphs is presented in [33]. The graph representation we adopt in this paper is the *Extended Reeb Graph* (ERG) proposed in [34] for triangle meshes representing closed surfaces embedded in \mathbb{R}^3 . The definition of ERG elements is based on a classification of the evolution of the level sets of the function f .

Each node represents a change of the topology of the contours. Note that in this definition, a node n corresponds to a region r instead to a critical point as in the classical Reeb graph definition; for this reason r is called a *critical* region. Then, the arcs code the adjacency among the nodes, i.e. given two nodes n_1 and n_2 corresponding to the regions r_1 and r_2 , respectively, the arc $e = (n_1, n_2)$ exists if it is possible to walk from r_1 to r_2 without crossing any other critical region, see [34] for details. Note that an ERG arc does not depend on the number of level sets crossed along the contour tracking. The salient feature of the ERG is the approximation of the RG through a finite number of level sets (63 in the experiments conducted in Section 5).

The most interesting aspect of RGs is their parametric nature. By changing f , we have different descriptions of the same surface \mathcal{S} that highlight different shape properties. Here we choose three alternative scalar functions f , namely the integral geodesic distance defined in [21] and the two distance functions $f(\mathbf{p}) = \|\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{b}\|_2$, with \mathbf{b} the center of mass and the center of the sphere circumscribing the triangle mesh respectively. Fig. 2 exemplifies our three ERG representations on a hand model, namely a) using geodesic distance, b) the distance from the mass center, and c) from the center of the circumscribing sphere. These distance functions are normalized, so that the graphs are invariant to scale.

In Table 1 we show some examples of graphs extracted from three different shapes: glasses, an octopus and a spring. Their nodes are placed without the original spatial distribution. This is not a standard representation of Reeb graph but we use it here in order to show that the graphs have no attributes or weights, neither on the nodes (which could be e.g. the spatial coordi-

Figure 2: Extended Reeb graphs using a) geodesic distance, b) the distance from the mass center, and c) from the center of the circumscribing sphere

nates), nor in the edges (which could be e.g. the distances between nodes in the original Euclidean space). Using unattributed graphs for characterizing shapes leads to a completely non-rigid comparison among objects, only based on structural relations. It is also important to note that the graphs have very different number of nodes, depending on the shape and on the Reeb-graph function. Therefore the measures or features extracted from the graphs have to be independent on the number of nodes, as far as possible.

3.2. Features from graph spectra

In the present work we organize graphs into a multidimensional pattern-space, where each dimension is a feature. This means that the coordinate of a pattern (a 3D shape) on some concrete dimension is given by the value yielded by the evaluation of a concrete feature on the pattern (the structure). The features have to be evaluated on all the graphs and the values returned define the embedding of the graphs into the new feature space. In order to map the structure of a graph onto a fixed-length vector we mainly use graph-

3D shape	Geodesic	Baricenter	Sphere

Table 1: Instances of graphs extracted from 3D shapes: glasses, octopus, spring. The graphs are unattributed and their spatial representation is arbitrary. They only express the relations between the nodes.

spectral decomposition methods. This kind of features essentially exploit the eigendecomposition of the adjacency matrix and the closely related Laplacian matrix [24]. The set of features taken into account is listed in what follows.

Spectrum of the adjacency matrix. Each component of the vector represents a different spectral mode of the original adjacency matrix \mathbf{A} and the order of the vectors depends on the associated eigenvalues.

Degree distribution. The degree distribution is a major source of statistical information for the characterization of a graph $G = (V, E)$. For instance, testing whether a graph is scale-free or not is posed in terms of checking whether its degree distribution follows the power law [35].

Subgraph node centrality. A more elaborate feature is the *subgraph node centrality* [36], which quantifies the degree of participation of a node i in structural subgraphs. It is defined in terms of the spectrum of the adjacency

matrix \mathbf{A} , i.e.

$$C_S(i) = \sum_{k=1}^n \phi_k(i)^2 e^{\lambda_k},$$

where $n = |V|$, λ_k the k -th eigenvalue of \mathbf{A} and ϕ_k its corresponding eigenvector.

Perron-Frobenius eigenvector. The eigenvector ϕ_n corresponding to the largest eigenvalue is the so called *Perron-Frobenius eigenvector*. The components of the latter vector denote the degree of importance of each node in a connected component and they are closely related to subgraph centrality [36]. Furthermore, the magnitudes $|\phi_k|$ of the (leading) eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} have been been experimentally validated for graph embedding [2].

Normalized Laplacian spectrum. Besides the study of the adjacency matrix, it is also interesting to exploit the *spectrum of the Laplacian* $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{D} - \mathbf{A}$ or better the *spectrum of the normalized Laplacian*:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathbf{D}^{-1/2} \mathbf{L} \mathbf{D}^{-1/2},$$

where \mathbf{D} is the diagonal degree matrix. These spectra encode significant structural information. For instance, the second eigenvalue λ_2 , either of L or \mathcal{L} , satisfies $\lambda_2 > 0$ for connected graphs and, thus, defines the *spectral gap*. The lower its value, the weakest the connectivity of the graph and vice versa. For \mathcal{L} , λ_2 satisfies the so called Cheeger inequality: $2h_G \geq \lambda_2 \geq h_G^2/2$, where h_G is the Cheeger constant [24]. It is defined as $h_G = \min_S h(S)$, where $S \subset V$ defines a partition of the vertices of the graph, and $h(S)$ is the Cheeger ratio:

$$h(S) = \frac{\text{cut}(S, \bar{S})}{\min(\text{vol}(S), \text{vol}(\bar{S}))}, \quad \bar{S} = V \setminus S.$$

Therefore, λ_2 is related to the optimal partitioning the graph, serving as a measure of the quality of such partition. Furthermore, the Laplacian spectrum plays a fundamental role in the design of regularization graph kernels. Such kernels encode a family of dissimilarity measures between the nodes of the graph [37].

Fiedler vector. The *Fiedler vector* is the Laplacian eigenvector corresponding to the first non-trivial eigenvalue, ϕ_2 in connected graphs. It encodes the connectivity structure of the graph (actually its analysis is the core of graph-cuts methods) and it is related to the Cheeger constant, as follows. The components of the normalized Laplacian Fiedler vector are positive if the corresponding vertex belongs to S in the approximately optimal $cut(S, \bar{S})$ (more precisely in the normalized cut [38]) and they are negative if the corresponding vertex belongs to \bar{S} .

Commute time. The eigenvectors and eigenvalues of the Laplacian enable the definition of a metric between the nodes of the graph, namely the *commute time*, $CT(i, j)$. It is the average time taken by a random walk starting at i to reach j and then returning. If we use the normalized Laplacian:

$$CT(i, j) = vol \sum_{k=2}^n \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \left(\frac{\phi_k(i)}{\sqrt{d_i}} - \frac{\phi_k(j)}{\sqrt{d_j}} \right)^2,$$

where vol is the volume of the graph, that is, the trace of \mathbf{D} , whereas d_i and d_j are the degrees of i and j respectively. Since the commute time is a metric, and because of its utility for graph embedding [39], the path-length structure of the graph is partially encoded.

Flow complexity. Finally, we consider diffusion kernels on graphs, which belong to the family of regularization kernels; indeed, the analysis of the diffusion process yields a valuable source of information concerning the structure of the graph. A recent characterization of the diffusion process is the *the flow complexity trace* [40], a fast version of polytopal complexity [41]. The complexity trace encodes the amount of heat flowing through the edges of G for a set of inverse temperatures β : from $\beta = 0$ (no flow) to $\beta \rightarrow \infty$ (flow equal to $\frac{2|E|}{n}$ for a graph of size n) there is a phase-transition point. More precisely, the instantaneous flow for a given β is

$$F(G; \beta) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j \neq i}^n A_{ij} \left(\sum_{k=1}^n \phi_k(i) \phi_k(j) e^{-\beta \lambda_k} \right),$$

and the trace element for this inverse temperature is the instantaneous complexity

$$C(G; \beta) = \log_2(1 + F(G; \beta)) - \log_2(n),$$

where the final term is for the purpose of size normalization. Other related heat descriptors include the heat kernel trace [42] and among the related spectral descriptors a good example are the symmetric polynomials, recently used to deal with co-spectrality [43].

When considering only spectral features for graph description we are aware of the risk of iso-spectrality. Although we cannot discard or reduce this risk by combining multiple spectral measures we will show that they may boost the effectiveness of a graph indexing method when iso-spectrality is explicitly addressed in advance. Another source of problems is the potential impact of 3D noise in the extraction of Reeb graphs. In a preliminary phase we have found a moderate intra-class variability of Reeb graphs, at

least in the 3D (SHREC) [1] database (see Fig. 3).

The sets of features listed above are transformed into histograms after normalizing them by the volume of the graph. Note that commute time is exploited twice: normalized linearly and quadratically; depending on the volume of the graph one of them is more descriptive than the other. After normalization, histograms are used in order to characterize the graph without dependence on the number and order of the nodes. Only the complexity flow curve is not histogrammed, for the sake of order preservation. Since there is no optimal strategy to select the number of bins, we perform several different binnings on each measure (2, 4, 6 and 8 bins). All the histograms form a bag of features, of size $9 \cdot 3 \cdot 20 = 540$ features (9 measures from 3 graphs, with 20 bins which come from four different histograms; see Fig. 1).

Although each feature has its own structural meaning, a detailed analytical study of their individual and joint performance would be unfeasible. We perform this analysis through the information-theoretic feature selection which we detail next.

4. Feature selection

In this section we first discuss different information-based criteria for feature selection (Subsection 4.1). We choose to use a mutual information criterion for feature selection which does not assume any independences among features. We explain that related work has an approach which is equivalent to mutual information under a restricted search order. Then, (Subsection 4.3) we elaborate on the differences between a forward and backward search order for feature selection. In the latter approach our mutual information

criterion is still valid and we show that backward feature elimination can outperform forward feature selection. A deeper analysis of the estimation method we use is detailed in the Appendix.

4.1. Mutual information criterion

There are some practical issues involved in the maximization of mutual information between the features and the classes. Nowadays feature selection problems deal with thousands of features, in a continuous feature space. Estimating mutual information between a high-dimensional continuous set of features and the class labels is not straightforward due to the entropy estimation problem. There exist graph-based methods which do not need the density estimation of the data, thus allowing to estimate the entropy of high-dimensional data with a feasible computational complexity.

The simplest approach is to limit the cost function to evaluate the mutual information between single features $x_i \in \vec{S}$ and the classes C :

$$I(\vec{S}^*; C) \approx \sum_{x_i \in \vec{S}} I(x_i; C) \quad (1)$$

Such cost could be effective for some concrete cases, for instance, when the features are independent. The expression of the mutual information of the optimal feature subset $\vec{S}^* = \{x_1^*, x_2^*, \dots, x_{N_{S^*}}^*\}$ of size N_{S^*} can be decomposed into the following sum:

$$\begin{aligned} I(\vec{S}^*; C) &= \sum_{i=1}^N I(x_i^*; C) - \\ &- \sum_{i=2}^N \left(I(x_i^*; \vec{S}_{1,i-1}^*) - I(x_i^*; \vec{S}_{1,i-1}^* | C) \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where x_i^* is the i^{th} most important feature and $\vec{S}_{1,i-1}^* = \{x_1^*, \dots, x_{i-1}^*\}$ is the set of the first $i-1$ best features, which have been selected before selecting x_i^* . This expression is obtained by applying the chain rule of mutual information (see Subsection 4.3, Eq. 5). The property from Eq. 2 is helpful for understanding the kind of trade-off between discriminant power maximization and redundancy minimization which is achieved by $I(\vec{S}_i^*; C)$. The first summation measures the individual discriminant power of each feature belonging to the optimal set. The second summation penalizes those features x_i^* which, together with the already selected ones $\vec{S}_{1,i-1}^*$, are jointly informative about the class label C . This means that if $\vec{S}_{1,i-1}^*$ is already informative about the class label, the the informativeness of the feature x_i^* is the kind of redundancy which is penalized. However, those features which are redundant, but do not inform about the class label, are not penalized.

An intermediate strategy was introduced by Vasconcelos [44]. They sequentially relax the assumption that the dependencies are not informative about the class. By introducing the concept of l -decomposable feature sets they divide the feature set into disjoint subsets of size l . The constraint is that any dependence which is informative about the class label, has to be between the features of the same subset, but not between subsets.

The assumption that the redundancies between features are independent of the class is not realistic in most classification problems. Following we analyse some approaches which do not make the assumption of Eq. 1. Instead they take into consideration the interactions between all the features. Peng et al. present in [29] an approach based on mutual information which does not make the assumption of Eq. 1. Instead of estimating the mutual information

$I(\vec{S}; C)$ between a whole set of features and the class labels (also called prototypes), they estimate it for each one of the selected features separately. On the one hand they maximize the relevance $I(x_j; C)$ of each individual feature $x_j \in \vec{F}$. On the other hand they minimize the redundancy between x_j and the rest of selected features $x_i \in \vec{S}, i \neq j$. This criterion is known as the min-Redundancy Max-Relevance (mRMR) criterion and its formulation for the selection of the m -th feature is:

$$\max_{x_j \in \vec{F} - \vec{S}_{m-1}} \left[I(x_j; C) - \frac{1}{m-1} \sum_{x_i \in \vec{S}_{m-1}} I(x_j; x_i) \right]. \quad (3)$$

This criterion is equivalent to estimating mutual information without the independence assumption. It can only be used in a greedy algorithm which in each iteration adds a single feature and decides whether to add it to the selected features set, or to discard it. This order of selection is called first-order incremental forward feature selection. An interesting property of this criterion is that, when applied with this order of selection, it is equivalent to estimating the multivariate mutual information between all the selected features and the class. A comparison is shown in the next subsection, in Fig. 11.

Our contribution is the proposal of a criterion which does not depend on the search order and needs no independence assumption. Thus we need to estimate mutual information in a multivariate way without assuming any independences between features:

$$I(\vec{S}; \vec{C}) = H(\vec{S}) - H(\vec{S}|\vec{C}),$$

where \vec{S} is a matrix of size $m \times n$ and \vec{C} of size $m \times 1$ where m is the number of samples and n the number of features of the feature subset. The estimation

of the Shannon entropy $H(\cdot)$ of a multivariate variable is possible thanks to the *bypass* entropy estimation methods.

4.2. Entropy estimation

Bypass entropy estimators estimate entropy directly from the data patterns based on their distances or spatial relation. Thus they bypass the estimation of a probability distribution (more details in Appendix A1). The development of the *bypass* entropy estimation methods has placed information theory into the state of the art of pattern recognition problems [28]. There are estimators based on minimal spanning tree (MST) graphs [45], based on the k -nearest neighbors graph [46] and based on a k -d partitioning of the pattern-space [47] (Appendix A2). The method based on minimal spanning trees is not straightforward in our case because firstly the Rényi α -entropy is estimated and then the Shannon entropy has to be extrapolated. The second estimation needs some parameters which depend on the nature of the data [48]. Given that we work with datasets with hundreds of features (dimensions) and a low number of samples, we prefer to use Leonenko's entropy estimator based on k -nearest neighbours.

Given the distances $\|x_i - x_j\|$ between the samples x_i and their respective k -NN x_j , the Kozachenko-Leonenko entropy estimator is given by:

$$\hat{H}(X) = -\psi(k) + \psi(N) + \log \frac{V_d}{2^d} + \frac{d}{N'} \sum_{i=1}^{N'} \log(2\|x_i - x_j\|), \quad (4)$$

where d is the number of dimensions (number of features), N is the number of samples, N' is the number of non-zero distances, k is the number of neighbors, V_d is the volume of the unit ball $\mathcal{B}(0, 1)$ and $\psi(\cdot)$ is the digamma

function. There are more details about this estimator in Appendix A3 and a comparison with the k -d tree partitioning estimator is presented in Appendix A4.

The multivariate estimation allows us to use the mutual-information based criterion with any kind of search order. This is an advantage not only because we can add or discard any number of features, but also because we can perform a backward feature elimination. In the next subsection we discuss why backward elimination is better than forward selection.

4.3. Greedy search: backward vs forward elimination

The term *greedy* refers to the kind of searches in which the decisions cannot be undone. In many problems the criterion which guides the search does not necessarily lead to the optimal solution and usually falls into a local maximum/minimum. This is the case of forward feature selection. Here we show some differences between a forward and a backward search order for feature selection.

Even though greedy searches can fall into local maxima, it is possible to achieve the highest mutual information possible for a feature set, by means of a greedy backward search. However, the resulting feature set which provides this maximum mutual information about the class, is usually suboptimal in terms of size: it is not necessarily the smallest one.

There are two kinds of features which can be discarded: irrelevant features and redundant features. If a feature is simply irrelevant to the class label, it can be removed from the feature set and this would have no impact on the mutual information between the rest of the features and the class. It is easy to see that the further removal of other features from the set is not

conditioned by the removal of the irrelevant one. This can be explained by using the chain rule of mutual information:

$$I(\vec{F}; C) = I(x_1, \dots, x_n; C) = \sum_{i=1}^n I(x_i; C | x_{i-1}, x_{i-2}, \dots, x_1). \quad (5)$$

The mutual information of a multi-dimensional variable and the class is decomposed into a sum of conditional mutual information terms. For simplicity, let us see an example with 4 features: $I(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4; C) = I(x_1; C) + I(x_2; C | x_1) + I(x_3; C | x_1, x_2) + I(x_4; C | x_1, x_2, x_3)$. If we decide to remove x_4 , it is because it provides no information about C , given the rest of the features, that is: $I(x_4; C | x_1, x_2, x_3) = 0$. Once removed, it can be seen that x_4 does not appear in any other terms, so, x_3 , for example, could be removed if $I(x_3; C | x_1, x_2) = 0$, without worrying about the previous removal of x_4 .

The artificial data set ‘‘Corral’’ [49] illustrates well the difference between forward and backward greedy searches with mutual information. In this data set there are 6 binary features, $\{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6\}$. The class label is also binary and it is the result of the operation $C = (x_1 \wedge x_2) \vee (x_3 \wedge x_4)$. Therefore x_1, x_2, x_3 , and x_4 fully determine the class label C . The feature x_5 is irrelevant, and x_6 is a feature highly (75%) correlated with the class label. Some samples are:

x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4	x_5	x_6	C
0	1	1	0	1	0	0
0	1	1	1	1	1	1
1	0	0	0	0	1	0
1	0	1	1	0	1	1

Most feature selection approaches, and in particular those which perform a forward greedy search, first select the highly correlated feature, which is

an incorrect decision. Contrarily, when evaluating the mutual information in a backward greedy search, the first features to discard are the irrelevant and the correlated ones. Then, only the four features defining the class label remain selected.

In practice, the mutual information estimation is not perfect; moreover, the train set usually does not contain enough information to completely define the distribution of the features. Then, rather than maintaining a zero decrease of the mutual information when discarding features, the objective is to rather keep it as high as possible, accepting small decreases. An experimental proof of the improved performance by a backward elimination process is discussed in Subsection 5.3.

5. Results and discussion

We perform experiments on a subset of the SHREC [1] benchmark, considering 300 models pre-classified in 15 classes \times 20 objects. Each 3D model has a class label $c \in \{human, cup, glasses, airplane, chair, octopus, table, hand, fish, bird, spring, armadillo, buste, mechanic, four-legged\}$. Previews of all the objects are shown in Fig. 3. We first analyze the classification performance (Subsection 5.1), and the importance of different features along the evolution of the feature selection process (Subsection 5.2). Then, we present some results which back-up some claims made in the previous section, namely we analyze the performance of backward feature elimination wrt forward feature elimination (Subsection 5.3). Finally (Subsection 5.4) we discuss how the results of this work can benefit graph indexing approaches.

Figure 3: The 3D shapes database [1].

5.1. Classification performance

Figure 4 shows the classification error on the SHREC database, measured by 10-fold cross validation (10-fold CV). For the 15-class problem, the optimal error (23, 3%) is achieved with a set of 222 features. This error is lower if classifying a lower number of classes: 10 classes (15, 5%), 5 classes (6%) and 2 classes (0%). The figure also shows that a high number of features degrades the classification performance. These results depend on the classifier used for measuring the error. In this case we use a k -nearest neighbours classifier,

which is an appropriate baseline for measuring the separability in data sets with a low number of samples.

In the same plot we show how the mutual information is maximized as the number of selected features grows, and its relation to the decrease in error. The mutual information curve, as well as the set of selected features, do not depend on the classifier, as it is a purely information-theoretic measure (however the classification error does depend on the classifier). In this work we do not propose a criterion for determining the optimal number of features. For this reason we show the whole process of feature elimination.

Figure 4: Classification errors.

5.2. Features analysis

Since several different unattributed graph measures are used in this work, we aim to determine which measures are the most important and in which combinations. To this end, we analyze the participation of each spectral feature in the classification of different sets of objects.

Figure 5 shows the evolution of the participation of the selected features. The coloured areas in the plot represent how much a feature is used with respect to the remaining ones (the height on the Y axis is arbitrary). For the 15-class experiment, in the feature sets smaller than 100 features, the most important is the Fiedler vector, *in combination* with the remaining features. Commute time is also an important feature. Some features that are not relevant (given the rest) are the node centrality and the complexity flow. Turning our attention to the graphs type, all three are relevant.

In the same picture, the dashed vertical line shows the 222-feature set, which yielded the lowest error in our experiments. For this optimal feature set, in Figure 6 we also detail the proportion of features selected. In the plot representing the selected binnings we can see that the four different binnings of the features do have importance for graph characterization.

Conclusions concerning the relevance of each feature cannot be drawn without performing some additional experiments with different groups of graph classes. For this purpose from Figure 7 to Figure 10 we present four different 3-class experiments. The classes share some structural similarities, for instance the 3 classes of the first experiment (*Human/Armadillo/Four-legged*) have a head and limbs; *Airplane/Fish/Bird* are thin, large and have wings/fins; *Cup/Bust/Mechanic* don't have many salient features; and *Chair/*

Figure 5: Feature selection on the 15-class experiment.

Figure 6: Feature statistics for the best-error feature set.

Octopus/ Table share the presence of thin long legs. Although in each experiment the minimum error is achieved with very different numbers of features, the participation of each feature is highly consistent with the 15-class experiment. The Fiedler vector is always the most important for feature sets smaller than 100. On the other hand, the commute time measure is not important for feature sets smaller than 20, but then it becomes as important as the Fiedler vector. The main difference is that node centrality is more important for discerning among elongated sharp objects: it is not relevant in the *H./A./F.* and *C./B./M.* experiments, but it is relevant for small feature sets in the *A./F./B.* and *Ch./O./T.* experiments. All three graph types are relevant but the *sphere graph* performs best for blob-shaped objects. This is illustrated by the experiments *H./A./F.* and *A./F./B.* where the *sphere graph* is not important, while in the *C./B./M.* and *Ch./O./T.* experiments it is the most important one.

5.3. Search order: backward vs forward feature elination

In Subsection 4.3 we discussed that for first-order greedy algorithms using the mutual information criterion, backward feature elimination is more efficient than forward feature selection (which is equivalent to mRMR). Backward feature elimination conserves better the mutual information in the presence of dependency . In what follows we empirically back-up our claims. This can be done since one of the novelties of our approach is the possibility to evaluate the multivariate-mutual-information based criterion with any search order and not only with a first-order forward feature selection.

The error plot (Figure 11) represents the 10-fold cross validation errors yielded by both feature selection orders: forward and backward. They were

Figure 7: Feature Selection on 3-class experiments: Human/Armadillo/Four-legged.

run on the same data set. Although there might be data sets for which the search order does not have such a big impact (e.g. if the features were independent), in this case it does, and the minimum error yielded by the backward search order is 25%, while the minimum error achieved by the forward search order is 34%. Note that feature selection did not work well (in terms of CV error) for the latter, because the minimum error is reached with a very large feature set, 534. Contrarily, the backward process obtained the minimum error with only 88 features. This is due to important differences between the selected features in both cases. See Figure 12 where the area plots represent the participation of each feature with respect to the others along the feature selection process: from 1 to 540 features. It can be observed that for very small feature sets, the forward strategy starts with bins of the

Figure 8: Feature Selection on 3-class experiments: Aircraft/Fish/Bird.

same feature, while the backward approach yielded more equilibrated feature sets containing different features.

5.4. Potential boosting of graph indexing

We claim that the inclusion of the results of the feature selection analysis discussed along the paper may be key to boost graph comparison methods, provided that iso-spectrality is neutralized in advance. Indeed, one of the authors has recently proposed a graph indexing method where iso-spectrality is explicitly addressed [50], and which exploits the most discriminative features obtained in the previous sections of this paper. The underlying idea is to transform a graph into a distribution of tensors (covariance matrices); each tensor corresponds to a partial subgraph, and partial subgraphs overlap (define a coverage). Each of the subgraphs relies on the most discriminative

Figure 9: Feature Selection on 3-class experiments: Cup/Bust/Mechanic.

features found in this paper: commute times, Fiedler and Perron-Frobenius vectors and node centrality. This selection is key to outperform the *entropic graph comparison* method [51] which is based on commute times and thus it is prone to iso-spectrality. In addition, entropic graph comparison outperforms state-of-the-art graph-matching/comparison methods like re-weighted random walks (both using node positions and only topology) tensor-based matching and graduated assignment.

6. Conclusions

The contributions of this work to graph classification are twofold. Firstly, it demonstrates the feasibility of multi-class classification based on purely structural spectral features. Secondly, an information-theoretic feature anal-

Figure 10: Feature Selection on 3-class experiments: Chair/Octopus/Table.

ysis suggests that similar features are selected for very different sets of objects. Moreover, the feature selection experiments show that even if the precision of the selection criterion is degraded, the most important features are still the same.

On the other hand this paper presents a feature selection method based on information theory. The method needs no parameters or assumptions about the data distribution. Beyond the feature selection criterion, we discuss the impact of the feature selection order on the obtained feature set. We show that the criterion based on mutual information performs better with backward feature elimination. Thus, an important contribution of the use of bypass entropy estimation is that it enables the multivariate estimation of mutual information within a backward feature elimination process.

Figure 11: Comparison of forward selection and backward elimination. 10-fold cross validation errors for all the feature set sizes produced by both search orders on the same data set

Figure 12: Comparison of forward selection and backward elimination. The participation of each type of feature during the process of forward feature selection (left) and backward feature elimination (right).

As future work we consider using attributed and directed graphs for improving classification accuracy. We also find it necessary to use a wider range of graph features, as well as other kinds of graph extraction methods. Regarding feature selection we want to establish an information-theoretic stopping criterion and analyze its relation to the lowest errors yielded by different classifiers. Finally, it is also interesting to test this graph-based approach on graphs extracted from images.

Appendix A. Entropy estimation from graphs

Entropy is a basic concept in information theory [27]. It is related to predictability with several possible interpretations. One of them is that entropy measures the amount of information that an event provides. For example, a very unusual event is more informative than a very probable and frequent event. A related interpretation is that entropy measures the uncertainty in the outcome of an event. In this sense, one very common event provides less entropy than many different but equiprobable events. Another interpretation is that entropy measures the sparseness in the probability distribution. Thus, an image with many different colours has a more sparse (and entropic) histogram than an image with a few colours, or with some limited range of colours.

In the following subsections we address the problem of estimating entropy from a set of data.

Appendix A.1. Bypass entropy estimation

Entropy estimation is critical in IT-based pattern recognition problems. The estimation of the Shannon entropy of a probability density given a set of samples has been widely studied in the past [52, 53, 54]. Entropy estimators can be divided in two categories: “plug-in” and “non plug-in”. Plug-in methods [55] first estimate the density function, for example, the construction of a histogram, or the Parzen’s windows method. The non plug-in methods [45], on the contrary, estimate entropy directly from a set of samples, bypassing the estimation of a density. The latter are also referred to as “bypass entropy estimation”.

With the plug-in methods a serious problem arises when the number of the dimensions of the data is high. Due to the *curse of dimensionality*, it is not possible to obtain a good estimate the underlying density of a set of samples when there are more than two or three dimensions. On the one hand, the number of samples needed to define the density increases exponentially. On the other hand, the density estimation methods have to be tuned depending not only on the number of dimensions, but also on the data. The Parzen’s windows approach, for example, is a widely used method for estimating pdfs for a finite set of patterns. It has a parameter which sets the width of the (usually Gaussian) kernels used in the method. An inadequate value of this parameter affects the resulting estimation. In [56] Viola and Wells propose a method for adjusting the widths of the kernels by iteratively maximizing the likelihood. However, the method does not perform well with high-dimensional patterns.

Among the bypass entropy estimation methods, the most commonly used

are those based on entropic graphs and nearest neighbors graphs. These methods are capable of estimating entropy despite a high number of dimensions of the data space. Entropic and neighbors graphs are based on distances between the data patterns; once calculated the distances, no matter how high-dimensional the space is, the problem is simplified to distance measures. Thus, the computational complexity does not depend on the dimensionality, but on the number of patterns. On the other hand, in the Parzen windows approach there is a problem with data sparseness. Gaussian kernels, for example, though being infinite, do not consider those samples which lie at a distance larger than three standard deviations, because their weight is close to 0. This effect is overcome when using entropic graphs for direct entropy estimation.

The most used methods in the state of the art of bypass entropy estimation are the minimal spanning trees and the k -nearest neighbour graphs. In both of them the vertices correspond to patterns in the feature space, and the length of the edges which connect those vertices, are the distances between patterns. A spanning tree graph is an undirected graph which connects all the vertices without cycles. The minimal spanning tree is the one which has minimum total sum of its edges. Entropy can be estimated from the weighted sum of those edges, as explained in the next section. The k -nearest neighbour graph is also undirected, however, it is not necessarily connected, and it is not acyclic. Its vertices are connected to the k nearest vertices. Thus, an important difference arises between the estimation based on minimal spanning trees and the based on k -nearest neighbour one. If a multimodal distribution has its modes separated enough, the nearest neighbour graph does not con-

nect them with any edge and the distance between both modes is not taken into account. Contrarily, the minimal spanning tree always establishes some connection between samples belonging to different modes of the distribution. A most recent estimation method which is based on k -d partitioning of the space also has the capability of capturing the distance between separated modes.

Appendix A.2. k -d partitions entropy estimation

In most bypass entropy estimators the most time-consuming operation are the calcula of distances. Recently Stowell and Plumbley [47] proposed an estimation method which relies on data spacing without computing the distances between the samples. It partitions the space in which the samples are defined, similarly to the k -d tree algorithm. For a d -dimensional random variable X with a pdf $f(x)$, let the partition of X be $A = \{A_j | j = 1, \dots, m\}$, with $A_i \cap A_j = \emptyset, \forall i \neq j$ and $\cup_j A_j = X$. In each partition A_j with a d -dimensional volume $v(A_j)$, the pdf is approximated as: $f_{A_j} = \frac{\int_{A_j} f(x)}{v(A_j)}$. The pdf $f(x)$ of the samples is unknown and it can be approximated in each partition as $p_j = n_j/n$, where n_j is the number of samples in the partition A_j : $\hat{f}_{A_j} = \frac{n_j}{nv(A_j)}$. This pdf estimator is consistent as $n \rightarrow \infty$ [57]. By means of it, the Shannon entropy, $H = -\int f(x) \log f(x) dx$ can be estimated with:

$$\hat{H} = \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{n_j}{n} \log \left(\frac{n_j}{n} v(A_j) \right).$$

The partitioning is performed recursively as in the k -d tree algorithm. At each level the data is split at the median along one of its dimensions. The dimensions are sequentially selected in each recursive call. The base case

happens when a uniformity criterion is satisfied, ensuring that the data points in each partition have uniform density. Thus, non-uniform partitions are divided further. Also, this criterion is not applied before having at least \sqrt{n} data points in each partition: the minimum number of levels is $\lceil \log_2(n)/2 \rceil$.

Appendix A.3. k -nearest neighbours entropy estimation

The k -nearest neighbour methods for entropy estimation [58, 59, 60] are another bypass entropy estimation approach which has a low computational complexity and is asymptotically consistent. Provided that these methods are based on distances, the k -NN approach is useful for high dimensionalities. Also, as happens with the MST-based methods, not having to estimate a density is an advantage in high dimensionalities.

In 1987 Kozachenko and Leonenko published the proofs [58] for convergence and consistence of k -NN estimators of differential entropy. Leonenko proves the weak convergence of their estimator, however in [61] it is argued that the proof is not correct and they present an alternative proof for strong convergence. In the extensive study [46] about Rényi and Tsallis entropy estimation, Leonenko et al. also consider the case of the limit of $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ for obtaining the Shannon entropy. Their construction relies on the integral

$$I_\alpha = E\{f^{\alpha-1}(\vec{X})\} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^d} f^\alpha(x) dx, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where f^α refers to the density of a set of n independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) samples $\vec{X} = \{X_1, X_2, \dots, X_N\}$. The latter integral is valid for $\alpha \neq 1$, however, the limits for $\alpha \rightarrow 1$ are also calculated in order to consider the Shannon entropy estimation.

Appendix A.3.1. Kozachenko-Leonenko entropy estimation

In order to explain the k -NN entropy estimation, let us look at the Shannon entropy formula

$$H(X) = - \int f(x) \log f(x) dx, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

as an average of $\log f(x)$, being $f(x)$ an existing pdf. The Shannon entropy estimator of Kozachenko-Leonenko [58], whose publication was previous to [46], provides a slightly different form. Its estimates return almost the same values when the data has several dimensions. Only for a very low dimensionality a small difference between [58] and [46] can be observed. This difference is not significant, for this reason in the experiments we only use [46].

The estimation of $\widehat{\log f(x)}$ would allow the estimation of

$$\hat{H}(X) = -N^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \widehat{\log f(x)} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

For this purpose the probability distribution $P_k(\epsilon)$ for the distance between a sample x_i and its k -NN is considered. If a ball of diameter ϵ is centred at x_i and there is a point within distance $\epsilon/2$, then there are $k - 1$ other points closer to x_i and $N - k - 1$ points farther from it. The probability of this to happen is

$$P_k(\epsilon) d\epsilon = k \binom{N-1}{k} \frac{dp_i(\epsilon)}{d\epsilon} p_i^{k-1} (1-p_i)^{N-k-1} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

being p_i the mass of the ϵ -ball and

$$p_i(\epsilon) = \int_{\|\xi-x_i\|<\epsilon/2} f(\xi) d\xi. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The expectation of $\log p_i(\epsilon)$ is

$$E(\log p_i) = \int_0^\infty P_k(\epsilon) \log p_i(\epsilon) d\epsilon \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$= k \binom{N-1}{k} \int_0^1 p^{k-1} (1-p)^{N-k-1} \log p \cdot dp \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$= \psi(k) - \psi(N), \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where $\psi(\cdot)$ is the well-known digamma function. If assumed that $f(x)$ is constant in the entire ϵ -ball, then the approximation

$$p_i(\epsilon) \approx \frac{V_d}{2^d} \epsilon^d \mu(x_i)$$

can be formulated. Here d is the dimension and V_d is the volume of the unit ball $\mathcal{B}(0, 1)$. From the previous approximation and using the expectation of $\log p_i(\epsilon)$, the approximation of $\log f(\epsilon)$ is

$$\log f(\epsilon) \approx \psi(k) - \psi(N) - dE(\log \epsilon) - \log \frac{V_d}{2^d}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

and finally,

$$\hat{H}(X) = -\psi(k) + \psi(N) + \log \frac{V_d}{2^d} + \frac{d}{N'} \sum_{i=1}^{N'} \log \epsilon_i \quad (\text{A.10})$$

is the estimation of $H(X)$, where

$$\epsilon_i = 2||x_i - x_j|| \quad (\text{A.11})$$

is twice the distance between the sample x_i and its k -NN x_j and $N' \leq N$ is the number of non-zero distances.

Appendix A.3.2. Approximate nearest neighbours

An efficient implementation of k -nearest neighbours is the ANN library [62]. It allows to set an error bound ϵ which is the ratio between the distance to

the reported point and the true nearest neighbour (from the set of the k closest neighbours). Internally ANN builds a kd -tree structure, whose cells are visited in increasing order of distance from the query point. A stop condition of the search algorithm occurs when the distance is closer than an error bound ε . This premature stop causes a decrease in the precision of the k -NN computation.

It can be shown that for the Kozachenko-Leonenko entropy estimator the error bound has to be $\varepsilon = 0$, otherwise the entropy estimation is severely degraded, especially when the number of dimensions is high. For each distance ϵ_i (Eq. A.11), there is a maximum relative error $\varepsilon_i \leq \varepsilon$, and the estimated distance is $\epsilon_i(1 + 2\varepsilon_i) \leq \epsilon_i(1 + 2\varepsilon)$. Considering the estimator $\hat{H}'(X)$ which is affected by these errors, it is bounded by:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H}'(X) &\leq -\psi(k) + \psi(N) + \log \frac{V_d}{2^d} + \frac{d}{N'} \sum_{i=1}^{N'} \log(\epsilon_i (1 + 2\varepsilon)) \\ &= -\psi(k) + \psi(N) + \log \frac{V_d}{2^d} + \frac{d}{N'} \sum_{i=1}^{N'} (\log \epsilon_i + \log(1 + 2\varepsilon)) \\ &= \hat{H}(X) + d \log(1 + 2\varepsilon) \end{aligned}$$

where $\hat{H}(X)$ is the estimator (Eq. A.10). The estimation error $d \log(1 + 2\varepsilon)$ depends on the number of dimensions d . In a high dimensional context it is preferable to set $\varepsilon = 0$.

Appendix A.4. Comparison

In this section we present an experimental comparative of the Kozachenko-Leonenko k -NN entropy estimator and the Stowell-Plumbley k -d partitioning entropy estimator. The estimator based on minimal spanning trees is not in-

cluded in the experiment due to its requirement to tune the optimal α^* for different ranges of dimensions.

For comparing the estimators, a number of different distributions can be generated. In the following experiments the entropy estimations are performed on data following the Gaussian (normal) distribution. The Gaussian distribution is the one which has maximum entropy relative to all probability distributions that have finite mean, finite variance and cover the entire real line (or real space of any dimension, for multivariate distributions). A multivariate Gaussian distribution is described by the pdf:

$$f_{\mathcal{N}}(x_1, \dots, x_N) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\frac{N}{2}} |\Sigma|^{\frac{1}{2}}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}(x - \mu)^\top \Sigma^{-1}(x - \mu)\right), \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where $|\Sigma|$ is the determinant of the covariance matrix Σ , which is a non-singular $d \times d$ matrix. The Gaussian is a useful distribution for entropy estimation experiments because it has a theoretical entropy value, which depends on the number of dimensions d :

$$H(f_{\mathcal{N}}) = \frac{1}{2} \log((2\pi e)^d |\Sigma|). \quad (\text{A.13})$$

The data generated for the experiments was generated with a covariance matrix with ones in its diagonal, that is, the identity matrix, $\Sigma = I_{d \times d}$. This means that the generating distribution has the same variance in all the d dimensions. However, the generated data does not have exactly the same variance because infinite data would be necessary to perfectly define the actual distribution. If the data samples are very sparse in their d -dimensional space, their actual covariance matrix Σ could be very different from I . In fact, as the number of dimensions d increases, the number of samples N necessary to define well the distribution, increases exponentially, it is the

curse of dimensionality. That is why in some figures we present both the theoretical value (Eq. A.13) for the covariance $\Sigma = I$, and the theoretical value for the real Σ calculated from the data points, after their generation.

This sparseness effect can be observed in Fig. A.13-top, where the theoretical entropy value for $\Sigma = I$ is a dotted line and the theoretical entropy value for the real Σ is plotted in continuous black line. For a low number of samples these values differ much more than for a high number of samples. The number of samples varies along the horizontal axis.

Fig. A.13-top also represents the estimation results of the k -NN estimator in blue, and the k -d partitioning estimator in gray. Both estimators become more consistent as the number of samples increases. Note that, for a fixed number of samples, the estimation of both estimators becomes worse as the number of dimensions increases. It can be seen that the data sparseness effect causes the k -d partition estimator to diverge much faster than the k -NN estimator.

The dimensionality effect causes entropy estimations to differ from the actual entropy of the data. This difference is present in both estimators and it can be observed in Fig. A.15-left. In this figure the entropy is measured for data consisting of the fixed number of 100 samples. These samples were distributed following a Gaussian distribution in spaces with different dimensionality, from 1 dimension to 200 dimensions. The discontinuous black line represents the theoretical entropy of the generating distribution.

In Fig. A.15-left we also represent several different k values for the k -NN estimator. (Note that the k in k -d partition is not a parameter, it just belongs to the name we use for referring to the estimator of Stowell and Plumbley.)

We use it to show that different k values offer quite a similar entropy estimation. In all the experiments we set $k = 5$ which has experimentally shown to be an appropriate value. However, the rest of the k values offer a similar results. In these plots, several different k values are represented in blue line, and only the $k = 5$ line is represented in black, in order to see that this value is consistent with the rest of k values. In the last plot of the figure it can be seen that the difference between them is very small.

A low number of samples, 100 in the experiment in Fig. A.15, is enough for entropy estimations in 1 or 2 dimensions. In 3 dimensions 100 samples are too few for defining well a Gaussian distribution and the estimation slightly differs from the actual entropy. The k -NN estimation keeps close to the theoretical for several dimensions more and its estimations differ when there are 9 or more dimensions. After that, both estimators present a similar tendency, getting more and more separate from the theoretical entropy.

All these observations are valid only for small sampled Gaussian distributions (100 samples). If we exponentially increase the number of samples the plots would present a similar behaviour, but there is an offset in the dimensions axis. In Fig. A.14 we represent a surface plot in which the vertical axis, again, represents the entropy, while the parameters of the surface are the number of samples and the number of dimensions. In the front view of the plot it can be seen that Kozachenko-Leonenko's k -NN estimator (blue surface) keeps close to the theoretical entropy value (black grid) only for the first 8 dimensions. It can also be seen that the Stowell-Plumbley's k -d partition estimator is far from the correct values unless there is a sufficient number of samples. In [47] they point out that a minimum of $N \geq 2^d$ samples are

needed in relation with the dimensionality (d) in order to produce a reasonable estimate. This effect is observed in the gray surface, whose curvature with respect to the samples changes depending on the dimensionality.

The uniform distribution is another entropy maximizing distribution. It is the distribution of maximum entropy from among those distributions whose samples have a finite range support, that is, a minimum and maximum in each dimension. The entropy of the uniform distribution depends on the number of dimensions d and on the size of the range of each dimensions, which is given by its upper and lower limits, $l_{d,2}$ and $l_{d,1}$, respectively.

$$H(f_U) = \log \prod_{i=1}^d (l_{i,2} - l_{i,1}). \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The k -d partitioning based estimator of Stowell-Plumbley is more adequate for the estimation of this kind of distributions, as it partitions a region of the space which is given by the bounding box of the data, that is, the limits of the range. In Fig. A.13-bottom an experiment with uniform distributions is represented. Their limits are $(l_{d,1}, l_{d,2}) = (0, 1)$ in any number d of dimensions. Then, according to Eq. A.14 the entropy of the distributions is 0 for any dimension. In Fig. A.13 the plots represent how the estimation of the entropy converges to the real entropy value (0 in this case), as the number of samples defining the distribution increases. The experiment is presented in four different dimensionalities and, as expected, in higher dimensions the convergence needs a higher number of samples. For a better illustration of the dimensionality effect on the estimation Fig. A.15-right represents the estimations of uniform distributions with a fixed number of samples (100), in different dimensions from 1 to 200. While the k -NN method estimates

higher entropies as the number of dimensions increases, the k -d partitioning estimator keeps a good lower bound of the entropy.

In conclusion, the bypass entropy estimators are appropriate for high-dimensional problems. Among the estimators based on graphs, the k -NN based estimator of Kozachenko-Leonenko offers a good alternative to the *MST* based estimators. However, the k -NN estimator may fail to capture well enough the entropy if the different modes of a distribution are very separate. The k -NN entropy estimator is useful for distributions in \mathbb{R}^d , while the Stowell-Plumbley's k -d partitioning entropy estimator is useful for distributions with a finite support. The latter tends to underestimate entropy, while Kozachenko-Leonenko's tends to overestimate it.

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Figure A.13: Comparison of the estimated entropy by the k -NN estimator and the k -d partitioning estimator. The distributions are, Top: Gaussians and Bottom: Uniform, in different numbers of dimensions, Left: 2D, center: 3D, right: 4D.

Figure A.14: Comparison of the estimated entropy of Gaussian distributions by the k -NN estimator and the k -d partitioning estimator. The vertical axis represents the entropy, while the parameters of the surface are the number of samples and the number of dimensions. k -NN estimator (blue surface); k -d partitions estimator (gray surface); theoretical Gaussian entropy (black grid). Front view (left) and rear view (right).

Figure A.15: Comparison of the estimated entropy by the k -NN estimator and the k -d partitioning estimator. The data for the experiment consist of distributions of 100 samples in a variable number of dimensions. Left: Gaussian distributions, Right: uniform distributions.